

NEWSLETTER

CONCILIARE: advancing with our goals!

Welcome to the ninth edition of our newsletter!

As we move forward with the project's activities, we are pleased to share recent updates and highlight our project members' involvement in several initiatives, events and publications. Enjoy reading!

PUBLICATIONS

- Cabecinhas, R., Macedo, I., & Lins, L. (Eds.), (2026). **Living Memories & Media. Memória Viva & Media.** Húmus Editora.
- Licata, L., Babińska, M., & Zian, Y. (2026). **“Can’t you see it?”: A Cultural Psychological Approach to the Role of Heritage in Shaping Collective**

Memory and Identity. In R. Cabecinhas, I. Macedo, & L. Lins (Eds.), (2026). Living Memories & Media. Memória Viva & Media (pp. 17-31). Húmus Editora.

- Kesteloot, C., & Landmeters, R. (2026). **Focus: Le Passé Colonial Etterbeekois.** In I. Degryse, B. Wayens, C. Kesteloot, & M. Degraeve (Eds.). Les noms de lieux à Bruxelles. Enjeux passés et présents (pp. 291-296). Leuven University Press & Éditions de l'Université de Bruxelles. Collection BSI Series.
- Zian, Y. (2026). **La décolonisation de l'espace public en Région bruxelloise: politiques, administrations et activistes.** In I. Degryse, B. Wayens, C. Kesteloot, & M. Degraeve (Eds.). Les noms de lieux à Bruxelles. Enjeux passés et présents (pp. 275-290). Leuven University Press & Éditions de l'Université de Bruxelles. Collection BSI Series.

CO-ORGANIZED EVENTS

“Colonialism, gender and memory in public space”

On April 29, Rosa Cabecinhas, Pedro Menezes and Júlia Vilhena participated in the cycle of open lectures organized by the Working Group on Visual Culture of the Portuguese Association of Communication Sciences (SOPCOM), in partnership with the Batalha Centre of Cinema, the Communication and Society Research Centre (CECS/UMinho), and the CONCILIARE project. With an opening by Nicoletta Mandolini, they presented the project's work on the decolonization of public space, highlighting the presence of controversial monuments across the landscapes of European cities and how they impact the collective memory.

“Colonial Heritages and Antiracism” with Christiane Taubira

On April 18, we welcomed Christiane Taubira, former Minister of Justice of France, to Brussels to discuss colonial heritage and antiracism. The cycle was organized by Mireille-Tsheusi Robert, from the FEMÏYA collective, supported by CONCILIARE and moderated by Gia Abrassart. Participants engaged in three moments of learning and discussion: a decolonial walking tour in Ixelles, a meeting at the Ixelles City Council, and a gathering with activists and members of progressive movements at the AfricaMuseum.

“Postcolonial?” inaugurates at the House of European History

The opening of the exhibition “Postcolonial?” took place on April 18, at the House of European History, in Brussels. Through this collaboration, we hope to see our research reach broader audiences and impact the community. The exhibition is free to access and will be on display until March 2027.

PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

CONCILIARE’s goals and results shared at ULB

On May 11, Chantal Kesteloot presented CONCILIARE at the International symposium "Contesting and negotiating memory in public space. Statues, place names and

symbols in debate in Belgium and Quebec". The next day, Laurent Licata and Yasmina Zian joined the conference "New research on Colonial and Postcolonial Africa: Manuscripts and journals, collections and museums", also sharing the project's purposes with the audience. Both events took place at ULB.

Lectures on decolonization of public space

On April 30, Yasmina Zian gave a lecture at the Katholieke University of Leuven on "Decolonising cultural heritage practices", part of the seminar "Cultural Heritage and Geopolitical Challenges". On March 23, she was a guest speaker at the seminar "Histories of the present time" at the University of Saint-Louis (UCL) in Brussels.

Discussions on social diversity and identity

Joaquim Pires Valentim and Emiliano Abad participated in the initiative "UNI(r)(di)VERSIDADE(s): Valuing Cultural Plurality in Academia", held at the University of Coimbra on April 15. Joaquim presented the panel "Cultural diversity: different and unequal", while Emiliano moderated the roundtable "Reflections from students' collective voices". In March, Emiliano also moderated the roundtable "Identity", hosted at UC as part of the cycle "Intersections: 6 dialogues to understand who we are". Presented as a member of CONCILIARE, he shared examples related to the project works during the discussion.

Anti-racist Festival

On March 20, the Université Libre de Bruxelles hosted an event featuring multiple debates, academic interventions and artistic presentations focused on the importance of fighting all forms of racial discrimination. Yasmina Zian and Maria Babińska represented CONCILIARE in the stand dedicated to introducing the project to the participants. They also joined presentation sessions, roundtables, and a podcast by the campus radio - [click here to listen](#).

UPCOMING EVENTS

From conservation to restitution: Return the Congo ancestors

Journée d'étude, de réflexion et de dialogue

De la conservation à la restitution :

Rendre les ancêtres du Kongo à leur terre

Mercredi 20 mai de 9h30 à 16h30
 Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique
 29 rue Vautier, 1000 Bruxelles
Inscription gratuite

to their lands

The Journey of Studies, Reflections, and Dialogues will take place at the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences in Brussels, on May 20, as a study day dedicated to discussing the return of ancestral remains to the Democratic Republic of Congo. The program explores research results on this topic, alongside debates with cultural and political speakers from the DRC and members of the Congolese diaspora.

This is an initiative of AfriqHope, in collaboration with MWASI asbl, the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Université libre de Bruxelles within CONCILIARE, University of Lubumbashi, UCLouvain, UCLouvain Saint-Louis Bruxelles, and ICOM Belgium/Wallonia-Brussels.

Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Paula Di Leone, Rosa Cabecinhas, Isabel Macedo and Emiliano Abad

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conciliaredigitalmedia@gmail.com

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